

Facile synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-(2*H*)-1,2,4-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxides promoted by samarium diiodide

W. K. Su^{a*}, B. B. Yang^a and C. L. Shou^b

^aCollege of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Zhejiang University of Technology, Hangzhou 310014, P. R. China

E-mail : suweike@zjut.edu.cn Fax : 86-571-88320420

^bEditorial Office, Zhejiang University, Hangzhou 310027, P. R. China

Manuscript received 20 November 2002, accepted 21 January 2003

A series of 3,4-dihydro-(2*H*)-1,2,4-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxides were synthesized in good yields via intermolecular reductive cyclization of *o*-azidobenzenesulfonamides with aldehydes and aliphatic ketones promoted by samarium diiodide under mild and neutral conditions.

Samarium diiodide has been developed as a mild, neutral and versatile single electron transfer reductant¹. It has been widely used in synthetic chemistry, especially in ring closure reactions, carbon-carbon bond formation reactions and stereocontrolled reactions². It is well known that azide compounds can be easily reduced by samarium diiodide to the corresponding amines³. However, little attention has been drawn on the intermediate derived from an azide group by samarium diiodide treatment⁴. Recently, we reported the reductive coupling of azide compounds with nitriles⁵, the reductive cyclization of *o*-azidobenzenamides with aldehydes and ketones as well⁶. 2*H*-1,2,4-Benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxide derivatives have attracted strong interest due to their biological properties⁷.

Here we report a facile synthesis of 3,4-dihydro-(2*H*)-1,2,4-benzothiadiazine-1,1-dioxides via intermolecular reductive cyclization of *o*-azidobenzenesulfonamides with aldehydes and aliphatic ketones promoted by samarium diiodide in good yields under mild and neutral conditions (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Results and discussion

The results are summarized in Table 1. When *o*-azidobenzenesulfonamides **1** and aldehydes or aliphatic ketones **2** were treated with 2 equivalents of samarium diiodide in anhydrous THF at room temperature under a

Table 1. Reductive cyclization of *o*-azidobenzenesulfonamides with aldehydes and ketones promoted by samarium diiodide

Sl. no.	X	R ¹	R ²	Time h	Yield ^a %
1.	H	<i>n</i> -Pr	H	2	87 (3a)
2.	H	<i>n</i> -C ₆ H ₁₃	H	3	84 (3b)
3.	H	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂	H	3	79 (3c)
4.	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	3	85 (3d)
5.	H	<i>p</i> -ClH ₂ OC ₆ H ₄	H	3	84 (3e)
6.	H	<i>m</i> -BrC ₆ H ₄	H	3	80 (3f)
7.	H	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₃	2	73 (3g)
8.	Cl	CH ₂ CH ₃	CH ₂ CH ₃	4	72 (3h)
9.	Cl	<i>n</i> -C ₅ H ₁₁	CH ₃	3	61 (3i)
10.	Cl		-(CH ₂) ₅ -	3	70 (3j)
11.	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	12	0 ^b
12.	Cl	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	12	0 ^b

^aIsolated yield based on azide compounds. ^bThe reaction were studied at room temperature and refluxing conditions, and *o*-aminobenzenesulfonamide was obtained with 91% yield.

nitrogen atmosphere, the deep blue color of the mixture changed to yellow immediately and the desired products **3** were obtained with satisfactory yields. Aromatic ketones have also been studied in our experiment (Sl. nos. 11 and 12). However, only *o*-aminobenzenesulfonamide was obtained and the desired products **3** were not detected even for a long time reaction at reflux conditions. *o*-Aminobenzenesulfonamides derived from compounds **1** were treated with aldehydes or aliphatic ketones **2** under the same conditions failed to obtain the desired products **3**. The detailed mechanism of the above reaction has not been clarified. The formation of products **3** may be described by the mechanism given in Scheme 2.^{5,8}

Scheme 2

Experimental

Tetrahydrofuran (THF) was distilled from sodium/benzophenone prior to use. All reactions were carried on under a dry nitrogen atmosphere. *o*-Azidobenzenesulfonamides were synthesized by diazotization of the corresponding amine followed by azidation of the resulting diazonium chloride with sodium azide⁹. M.ps. are uncorrected. Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 683 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra (CDCl₃) on a Bruker AC-80 instrument (*J* values in Hz, chemical shifts expressed in ppm downfield from internal tetramethylsilane) and mass spectra on a HP 5989B spectrometer. Microanalysis was carried out on a Carlo-Erba 1106 instrument.

General procedure: A solution of the azide compound **1** (1 mmol) in anhyd. THF (3 ml) was added to Sml₂ (2 mmol) at room temperature under dry nitrogen atmosphere. The deep blue color of the mixture changed into yellow immediately. Then the aldehyde or ketone **2** (1.2 mmol) was introduced. After being stirred for a certain time (Table 1), the reaction mixture was treated with 0.1 *N* HCl and then extracted with ethyl acetate (3×30 ml). The combined organic extracts was washed with saturated aq. Na₂S₂O₃, then brine and dried over anhyd. MgSO₄. After the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure, the crude products were purified by preparative TLC on silica gel using ethyl acetate-cyclohexane (1 : 1) as eluent : **3a**, m.p. 105–106° (lit.¹⁰ 106–107°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3365, 3215, 3030, 2980, 2930, 2890, 2850, 1605, 1575, 1500, 1470, 1370, 1160, 740; δ_{H} 0.85–1.80 (7H, m, CH₂CH₂CH₃), 3.96 (1H, br s, NH), 4.11 (1H, br s, NH), 4.61–4.80 (1H, m, CH), 6.53–7.57 (4H, m, ArH); **3b**, 120–122° (lit.¹¹ 122°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3362, 3220, 3015, 2980, 2930, 2875, 2835, 1610, 1582, 1500, 1465, 1365, 1145, 742; δ_{H} 0.85–1.83 (13H, m, (CH₂)₅CH₃), 3.96 (1H, br s, NH), 4.13 (1H, br s, NH), 4.66–4.82 (1H, m, CH), 6.53–7.57 (4H, m, ArH); **3c**, 166° (lit.¹¹ 167°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3352, 3208, 3010, 2930, 2845, 1610, 1582, 1500, 1470, 1365, 1155, 735; δ_{H} 3.10 (2H, d, *J* 6.0 Hz, CH₂), 4.05 (1H, br s, NH), 4.16 (1H, br s, NH), 4.76–4.87 (1H, m, CH), 6.56–7.67 (9H, m, ArH); **3d**, 147–

148° (lit.¹² 148°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3385, 3208, 3010, 1610, 1582, 1500, 1365, 1155, 1050, 735; δ_{H} 5.75 (1H, br s, NH), 6.16–6.32 (1H, m, CH), 6.76–7.64 (9H, m, ArH), 8.03 (1H, br s, NH); **3e**, 163–164° (lit.¹³ 164–165°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3392, 3210, 3015, 2980, 2860, 1610, 1582, 1510, 1385, 1245, 1150, 740; δ_{H} 3.68 (3H, s, CH₃), 4.20 (1H, br s, NH), 4.47–4.59 (1H, m, CH), 5.20 (1H, br s, NH), 6.67–7.74 (8H, m, ArH); **3f**, 167–168° (Found : C, 45.97; H, 3.33; N, 8.16. C₁₃H₁₁BrN₂O₂S calcd. for : C, 46.03; H, 3.27; N, 8.36%); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3395, 3220, 3010, 1600, 1575, 1500, 1325, 1155, 1085, 825, 735; δ_{H} 5.05 (1H, br s, NH), 5.62–5.80 (1H, m, CH), 6.76–7.95 (8H, m, ArH), 9.85 (1H, br s, NH); *m/z* 340 (M+2, 48.5), 338 (M⁺, 48), 259 (20.8), 183 (20.5), 156 (46.5), 108 (35), 93 (67.2), 92 (100), 77 (12.7), 76 (12.5), 51 (7.7); **3g**, 178–180° (lit.⁸ 178–180°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3350, 3210, 3010, 2980, 2865, 1610, 1575, 1510, 1470, 1385, 1160, 740; δ_{H} 0.95 (3H, t, *J* 7.0 Hz, CH₃), 1.50 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.68–2.01 (2H, m, CH₂), 5.00 (1H, br s, NH), 5.12 (1H, br s, NH), 6.47–7.67 (4H, m, ArH); **3h**, 164–165° (lit.⁸ 164–166°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3350, 3230, 3010, 2980, 2955, 2875, 2850, 1500, 1470, 1385, 1160, 705; δ_{H} 0.95 (6H, t, *J* 6.5 Hz, 2 × CH₃), 1.72 (2H, q, *J* 6.5 Hz, CH₂), 2.25 (2H, q, *J* 6.5 Hz, CH₂), 6.20 (1H, br s, NH), 6.50 (1H, br s, NH), 6.68–7.50 (3H, m, ArH); **3i**, 131–133° (lit.⁸ 130–132°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3356, 3200, 3010, 2980, 2920, 2875, 2845, 1600, 1580, 1505, 1470, 1385, 1160, 702; δ_{H} 0.85 (3H, t, *J* 6.0 Hz, CH₃), 1.50 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.36–2.52 (8H, m, (CH₂)₄), 5.53 (1H, br s, NH), 5.67 (1H, br s, NH), 6.52–7.60 (3H, m, ArH); **3j**, 189–190° (lit.⁸ 190–192°); $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$ 3370, 3275, 3010, 2980, 2930, 2870, 2840, 1605, 1580, 1500, 1470, 1365, 1150, 703; δ_{H} 1.60–2.50 (10H, m, (CH₂)₅), 4.68 (1H, br s, NH), 5.25 (1H, br s, NH), δ_{H} 4.42–7.40 (3H, m, ArH).

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Center of Engineering Research of Zhejiang University of Technology for financial help.

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